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UNFOLDING CENTRINNO'S PROJECT FRAMEWORK

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Co-designing regenerative processes to collectively construct pathways towards productive cities

Humans today recognize the environmental damages provoked by the Anthropocene and the increasing consequences of the adoption of the industrial machinism, mass media industries and digital and algorithmic technologies. In parallel with the rise of comfort and technological progress over the past decades that make lives easier for a large part of the population, individuals now have to grapple with alienation exacerbated due to technologies, the polarisation of power, disconnection from their environment and knowledge deprivation. There is a clear need for creative processes that engage people in knowledge acquisition on how to do and make, how to live, and how to conceptualise and theorise to be able to face current societal challenges and avoid massive cognitive degeneration. At a collective scale, this also asks for caring about how the means of production and work situations and systems impact the well-being of people and the natural ecosystems in which they evolve. After years of research and innovation practices in mainstream and alternative economies, it is still hard to define the outlines of convivial technologies and more appropriate forms of sustainable production. Such complex issues require time and space for collective experimentations to be better explored and documented.

The work initiated by the maker movement within the Fab City Initiative is a grounded niche of emerging practices for locally productive models at

city/regional scales, where people are in constant search for more circularity, openness and inclusion in the way cities produce what they consume; these practices benefit from global peer-learning to share knowledge, designs and experiences. In parallel with the development of the Fab City Strategic Action Plan, curious researchers and practitioners initiated CENTRINNO, a collaborative research project that zooms into the creative regeneration of historic industrial areas, intuiting that understanding the past of productive areas and their associated forms of making is key to foresee the potential for productive activities in the future. The project aims to use heritage as a catalyst for innovation and social inclusion, boosting a diverse, inclusive, and innovative urban economy, holding true to the ecological challenges of our time.

In this paper, the authors introduce CENTRINNO's conceptual framework as an overarching structure for experimentation that enables sharing, exchanging, and discussing the urban regeneration of historic industrial areas. It relies on place-based experimentation that intervenes systemically among five core concepts (circular economy, social inclusion, vocational training, innovation spaces and heritage) and across three action areas (ecosystem mapping, community development and Fab City Hubs Implementation).

Based on three years of action and research of iterative design and experimentation, CENTRINNO's framework is presented as a compass for local change agents to co-design regenerative processes in urban areas and reflect on their practices, sharing lessons learnt, research gaps and new opportunities that enable local systemic changes towards convivial forms of production.

KEYWORDS: regenerative design, systemic practices, productive cities, co-creation

RSD TOPIC(S): Case Studies & Practice, Learning & Education, Society & Culture

Introduction

Daily activities can be seen as a dynamic constellation of people's interactions with complex artefacts composed by assembled materials that have proper lifecycles and stories of living. Rethinking current production models cannot escape the questions of what objects are present in people's living places, why they were designed, their fabrication processes, how they are currently used and what they might become in the future.

The evolution of production processes across centuries is aligned with scientific and technological development, moving from manual techniques to more automatized forms of manufacturing. While initially improving certain forms of comfort as well as increasing accessibility to manufactured goods and services to a wider part of the population, the industrialization and globalisation of societies has led to multi-faceted crises and substantial losses for manufacturing capacity in certain geographical areas, reducing the autonomy of territories and making them fragile and less resilient ^[1]. Several authors ^[2-5] cautioned about the importance of reflecting on the social role of technologies and on how their misuse could provoke unexpected impacts such as alienation, skill loss, inequalities, and environmental degradation. This resonates with the need to be collectively responsible for more sustainable production systems, to have an understanding of what is produced globally while better enabling local production and appropriate forms of fabrication. Cities and regions with their respective ecosystems of craftsmen and manufacturers are now placed at the core of transformation enabling local production. Meanwhile, cities and regions are navigating through times of transition^[6]. Local production is seen as one challenge among many and needs to be integrated in current transition systems with specific needs, constraints, cultures, and plans ^[7].

The main objective of the paper is to **address how local ecosystems of stakeholders in neighbourhoods and cities can collectively share knowledge and experiment in the transition towards productive and regenerative territories**. This considering (1) the diversity of challenges they might face in their local contexts, and (2) the use of appropriate systemic approaches to reveal the complexity and interdependencies of such transformational phenomena.

(1) Diversity of challenges related to productive and regenerative territories

When initiating a collective process of transformation in a defined place and engaging new reflections on local production and self-sufficient ways of living, many challenges could emerge, including features from the past and present, future aspirations. This study focuses on five main challenges: Circular Economy, Social Inclusion, heritage, Innovation Spaces and Vocational Training. (See Figure 1)

Figure 1: Key concepts for re-activating local production ^[8]

Circular Economy. Cities are becoming more aware of their environmental impacts and are reinventing the relation between natural ecosystems and anthropocentric activities. Regenerative and circular economies support this reinvention through employment of methods and tools that help people better understand the socio-material realities of their areas (zooming into the flows of resources and on people engaged in transforming them) and assist in designing relevant action plans to reduce waste, close material loops and activate new synergies between local stakeholders (Furlan et al., 2022; Nohra & Barbero, 2019; Parisi et al., 2021). Each productive activity (new or existing) would benefit from a better knowledge of territorial resources and discovery of alternative

circular flows that move away from the dominating consumption patterns, based on extraction and depletion of resources, pollution, and generation of waste on a massive scale. Engaging in multi-stakeholder processes, onboarding courses, material flow analysis ^[13], cartographies ^[14], holistic analysis ^[9] network mapping, circular design workshops, and match-making events and platforms, local stakeholders become familiar with circular economy and integrate new expertise, opening up their network to urbanists, ecologists, and eco-designers that support them in measuring impact and finding new opportunities.

Social Inclusion. Current systems generate social inequalities and complex phenomena in cities such as gentrification, disengagement, and identity loss that can increase isolation or emphasise violent or antisocial behaviours. Certain jobs and associated modes of living were devalued by mainstream society creating new forms of poverty for farmers, artisans and other professionals taking part in primary and secondary activity sectors. Caring about citizen well-being demands a critical look at what is unbalanced in current systems to make visible the invisible, to take action moving towards fair treatment for all, and to create safe spaces for people to feel belonging within communities and contribute to territorial transformations. Cities are developing a wide range of social and solidarity policies and experimenting with new mechanisms that support the inclusion of disadvantaged or vulnerable groups and the participation of existing populations in decision-making processes. When working jointly in defining common values around new collective identities, people engaged in social innovation processes are invited to decenter from their beliefs, learn about non-violent forms of communication, and open themselves to other visions that value diversity, and embrace differences. New forms of production cannot ignore social inequalities and the tensions they generate, and it is worth anticipating them by actively developing abilities to co-create locally ^[15], to develop shared models of governance ^[16,17] and to engage in learning within wider international networks ^[18]. Social inclusiveness can be increased by targeting a mixed audience (in terms of age, cultural background, socioeconomic status, etc.), by explicitly including vulnerable or marginalised groups in their activities, and by actively involving communities in local and global events ^[19].

Innovation places. From idea emergence to socially accepted solutions, innovation processes are complex moments for conceptualising, prototyping, testing, translating, and collectively negotiating emerging products, services, and policies. With the rise of open innovation practices in public and private institutions, a new typology of spaces has been put at the forefront inside cities: third places like creative hubs, living labs, co-working spaces, fab labs, makerspaces and hackerspaces, educational labs, biolabs, foodlabs, and textile labs are described in ^[19] as “hybrid, fluid and evolutive, simultaneously physical, digital, social and political spaces. They also evolve and transform over time, according to their specific context and the interactions they establish locally and globally with their communities.” More recently, the concept of Fab City Hubs has been defined as sites of renewed meanings of production, knowledge, and innovation. As possible extensions of existing spaces, they act as ecosystem activators and/or physical places to access the network and platforms of distributed ecosystems. They also function as complex organisms enabling community resiliency ^[20]. New forms of production are then experimented with in those spaces from the bottom-up through collective practices of prototyping and direct connections with technologies. They can be co-designed to scale into a specific territory with a local expanded network of other craft and manufacturing places as well as scale out in the context of a node connected to distributed networks. Success of such places can be measured by their ability to create a collective vision, to connect with a glocal community and develop and maintain an appropriate infrastructure for the users of the place.

Heritage. Even with the improvement of technologies for real-time capture and digital archiving, it is impossible to build an exhaustive memory of what is happening on a daily basis inside cities. This means that an important part of what is experienced is disappearing: thoughts, forms of making, entire buildings, or waste. In the context of innovation, it is mainly the final artefacts in situations of uses that will be remembered in collective memories while stories of innovators will at times be preserved and disseminated as inspiration. What remains also has an emotional component. Production techniques might not evoke the same emotions according to the context in which they are used: a 50-year-old textile-maker with injuries in her hands will not have the same feeling of a curious designer practising spinning and weaving for the first time.

Cultural heritage is defined by the meaning given to both tangible and intangible heritage of a group or society that is inherited from past generations. At regional and city level, built heritage is considered for preservation by policy makers, researchers, cultural institutions, and experts that elaborate strategies for conservation and curation. Dedicated museums, exhibitions, monuments, and books are designed to share traces from the past. Restoring an abandoned meat factory, archiving long forgotten textile workers' songs, or revitalising traditional ways of urban farming are all examples of curating the past in a context of heritage. Keeping the old techniques of production alive as well as reviving the stories from craftsmen, manufacturers, and citizens can contribute to a better shared understanding of the impacts of respective production systems and help to reflect on future scenarios. Existing knowledge and ethnographic studies ^[21] are already nurturing design processes in that they allow access to a richer picture of the context. Creating bridges between cultural heritage strategies, stakeholders and the development of local production capabilities can be beneficial for cities as it can foster the emergence of new opportunities at the intersection between industrial tourisms, cultures, and new productive activities. Tools like emotional networking ^[22] and Living Archive ^[23] can help local stakeholders dig deeper into the histories of the complex ecosystem of human and non-human actors who impact their territory. A better understanding of stories from diverse perspectives and the impact of physical traces from the industrial past can function as a catalyst for an inclusive and sustainable future.

Vocational training. Transitions toward locally productive systems require the preservation of specific skill sets of knowledge while developing new competencies that create new profiles of professionals. In cities, this transformation will happen in collaboration with traditional vocational education systems, engineering schools, employment agencies, strategic policies supporting the relocation of productive activities and the ecosystem of makers, companies, and entrepreneurs. Programs for professionals and citizens include innovative pedagogical methods for un-learning, reconnecting with physical reality, practising hands-on making and digital fabrication in tandem with development of soft skills for innovation, collaboration, and entrepreneurship. As an example, specific skills and jobs are emerging from the development of circular systems. Many activities are situated across the life cycle of

materials, products and services that can be transformed in new job opportunities: resource management, material transformation, design and fabrication, production and logistics, distribution, use services, and end-of-life management. Agricultural and fabrication jobs from food, textile, wood, electronics, ceramics, and paper sectors need to be revalued, to be both more attractive for young professionals as well as be economically viable. Mutualized and nomadic forms of work are explored in cities that may allow for more balanced systems between fieldwork, administration, and research. Multiple forms of learning are now present in cities, from formal and informal education systems to physical or virtual learning strategies. One of emerging original practices is open schooling ^[24], an approach in which purposeful collaborations are built between schools and their wider communities. Educational ecosystems are collaborating to create experiences for lifelong learning, fostering multi-vocational education that embraces the diversity of new forms of living in cities.

(2) Systemic approaches to reveal complexity and foster collaborative experimentation

Even if circular economy, cultural heritage, innovation spaces, social inclusion, and vocational training are concepts closely related with one another, they are generally considered separately with few gateways between each other, and are rarely linked directly to the matter of local production.

On one hand, cities still face a plethora of administrative barriers, including the phenomena of silo that results in low levels of cross-collaboration between departments and with stakeholders mobilised in each respective program and action. This generates many systems that occur in parallel with different rhythms, dedicated ecosystems of stakeholders and programs of action that take a role in territorial transformations. There are gaps remaining to synchronise actions and optimise the engagement and proximity of stakeholders ^[25] in sharing integrated territorial visions.

On the other hand, the topic of production has been mainly associated with economic development departments that have specific indicators that do not primarily value the importance of situated environmental impacts. Production capabilities are currently analysed at industrial ecosystem and company level (micro) or national state level (macro) with either territorial or sectoral approaches that combine engineering and

economic methods. Such approaches are rarely adapted for city and regional scales or fail to capture the complex and changing metabolism of cities.

Moreover, there are multiple forms of urban transformation processes occurring in a specific territory and that can mobilise a strong diversity of stakeholders and multiple communities. Such processes can be situated between top-down or bottom-up approaches, distributing different roles and responsibilities to people involved in the process, including public administration.

Important systemic gaps are present in such contexts that prevent effectively activating and sustaining city level transformations. In this paper, authors question how urban ecosystems can embrace systemic thinking to co-create design interventions towards locally productive cities that bridge current silos and discuss the topic of production in a broader sense. They proposed to present and reflect on ongoing action-research that is part of the European project CENTRINNO. After describing the project and its research methodology, a systemic framework will be presented and completed by a synthesis of its uses across the project for peer-learning and specific interventions in nine different places across Europe.

Action-research in the context of the CENTRINNO project

This research is the fruit of collaboration between academic researchers, makers, architects, urbanists, public agents, and designers that participated in collective experimentation on the topic of urban regeneration, with a focus on historical industrial centres. The CENTRINNO project (New CENTRAlities in INdustrial areas as engines for inNOvation and urban transformation) is an action-research that last 3,5 years, involving 26 partner institutions, including city administrations and public institutions, university and research institutes, foundations, and Fab Labs from 10 EU countries. CENTRINNO contributes to the EU Commission research strategy as part of the Innovation and Research H2020 program on Cultural Heritage for societal challenges (Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials). It looks at transforming historic urban areas and cultural landscapes into hubs of entrepreneurship and social and cultural integration ^[26].

The project took its origin in the Fab City Global Initiative (2016), an emerging international network of 49 cities and regions that challenge themselves to produce everything they consume by 2054. The network is facilitated by the recently created Fab City Foundation, who is in charge of communicating about the network, its vision and strategic agenda with adapted media (book, online manifesto), and that supports peer-learning exchanges between cities through events, resource sharing, platforms and collaborative projects. As an emerging idea, the approach needs to be tailored by each city that is now transformed as a place for prototyping and experimenting with strategies to become locally productive. Prior to CENTRINNO, the main methodology developed by the network was the Fab City Strategic Action Plan ^[28], used as distributed innovation and research roadmap and based on the metaphor of the Full-Stack to unpack the Fab City vision into smaller parts, from the development of technological and learning infrastructures to the design of urban planning strategies and impact monitoring platforms. The CENTRINNO project was born within the necessity to better equip cities in the development of roadmaps and to nurture distributed actions with a common playground for research and learning.

The project was built on a conceptual framework entitled the CENTRINNO Framework and a methodological approach that permitted nine pilots from nine geographical areas to implement local strategies and missions and succeed in developing a series of resources that aimed to support agents to initiate and consolidate the systemic transformations of their territory. The project development followed three iterative phases of pilot experimentation where pilot cities, guided by a group of supporting partners, designed action plans, developed a series of missions and made impact assessment and adjustments (see Figure 2). The objective of the experimentation phase was to test strategies and actions in parallel to gain knowledge on key relevant concepts and have a broader systemic impact on each territory.

Figure 2: CENTRINNO cycles of experimentation ^[29]

Since its inception, the CENTRINNO Framework has been used in different situations and has experienced many transformations, serving the overall development of the project. In this article, authors trace back the uses of the CENTRINNO Framework during each stage of the project and reflect collectively on its relevance for various purposes. Authors (A1-A6) took active part in the research with supporting roles (project coordinator, scientific manager, work package leader, pilot coordination leader or local pilot manager). They contributed to most of the activities presented and took part in activity reporting and collective moments of exchanges. (see Table 1).

Table 1: Data collection synthesis

Stage	Collected data	Framework use(s)	Role of authors
Emergence	EU Proposal and grant agreement Informal exchange with scientific manager	Conceptual framework for locally productive cities	A1 - A3 Participation in preparation meeting and revision.
Collective vision	Whitepaper ^[8] Framework ^[29] CENTRINNO website (<i>Centrinno - Industrial Citizen Revolution</i> , 2020)	Operating framework for distributed experimentation	Redaction from A4. Participation in design A2, A5, A6
Resources	Framework Gitbook ^[31] Cartography ^[14] Living Archive ^[23] Fab City Hub (FCH) toolkit ^[20]	Main architecture to develop each infrastructures as an interconnected	Redaction from A4. A2 lead FCH A1 A5 A6 use and design

		branch	
Local pilots	Reporting of phase 1 & 2 [32,33]	Compass for local experimentations - in design and evaluation phase	A5: report and pilot coordination lead A2-A6 local pilot participant
Impact strategy	Evaluation methodology and Impact assessment reports [34,35]	Five concepts integrated as core strategies for the theory of change	A2-A4 Participation in design and review A2-A5-A6: Contributions
Policies and communication	Focus groups presentation Website tagging system	As dissemination tool	A3 lead Contributions from other authors

Stories of uses of the CENTRINNO Framework

Its emergence: designing common research structure

First designs of the framework occurred at the proposal stage through a series of collective meetings and sketching, connecting the dots between dedicated expectations from the respective European call, the areas of partner's expertise and the Fab City needs. At this stage, the framework was divided into five interconnected areas and was resource-oriented (cartography, school, network, blueprint and a living archive) to comply with the main target's expectations: the proposal reviewers.

Figure 3: CENTRINNO Framework premises

An operating framework for distributed experimentation

During the first months of the project, the consortium became familiar with CENTRINNO's approach and defined a more operational version of the framework. It took the shape of a spiderweb with the five key concepts (see Figure 1) combined with three levels of territorial actions that could initiate and consolidate local transformations towards productive cities, from the perspective of historic industrial sites. It consisted of local ecosystem mapping, community building and Fab City Hub implementation. The three action areas are seen as not linear and correlative and permit to integrate and position various levels of actions for each concept.

Figure 4: The CENTRINNO framework ^[31]

The format was designed to be able to position various elements such as tools, methods, and single activity (see orange points in Figure 5). It also allows positioning missions that crosscut different concepts or levels of actions (see grey zone in Figure 5). The framework was used in two cycles of co-creation activities with all partners to onboard them in the project, making them the first test-bed of the framework. It was also used to position a first collection of methods and tools, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: CENTRINNO's framework as collection of tools, methods and micro-missions (template and example) ^[29]

The baseline architecture for resource and expertise development

The resources are defined as enablers of the five main concepts. For each concept, one key resource was developed by one referent partner, in an iterative way. The referent partners were acting as experts, concept developers, resource developers and support for local pilots. The framework served as a baseline for the resource developers that were responsible for defining their own areas of intervention (see Figure 6) and deepening the knowledge of their own concept's branch. For instance, the resource allocated to *Heritage*, entitled the *Living Archive*, is supporting the three levels of actions and feeds stories for other concepts, mainly supporting community building. During the project, each deliverable situated its work within the framework, particularly positioning it among the concepts.

Figure 6: Meta-structure of the resources and example of the intervention area for the resource "Living Archive".^[29]

A compass for local experimentations - in design and evaluation phase

Each pilot city used the framework in their local context. After a phase of learning, they applied it with their ecosystem of stakeholders. The framework was mainly used for planning and designing their action plan and for evaluation in each of the three missions' cycles. Figure 7 presents the visualisation of the nine pilot cities' evaluation after phase 1 and 2. The framework helped to understand the diversity of strategies followed by each pilot and make visible their progress, in the blue zones.

Figure 7: Results of pilot experimentation phase 1 and 2

[32,33]

Five concepts integrated as core outcome areas for the theory of change

The framework was one core input in the design of the evaluation methodology. Partners used the model of the theory of change [36] where they discussed how to integrate the diverse dimensions of the framework. The five key concepts of the CENTRINNO framework were translated as outcome areas of socio-economic and cultural activity in which pilots attempt to influence change. (see the “If we - what we

will do” in Figure 8). Partners went further in defining key strategies for each concept and analysed the first results of the experimentations per pilot and at project level, retrofitting a better application of knowledge for each concept.

Figure 8: CENTRINNO's theory of change with integrated concepts ^[35]

A tool for communicating widely: The core concepts of CENTRINNO's framework were used to communicate the narrative of the project and engage with a wider audience in contributing to the project. The CENTRINNO website presents the concepts on the main page and the communication team created a tagging system to simplify the access of resources classified according to the concepts. In the last year of the project, a series of focus groups were organised to open the research to researchers, policy makers and any stakeholders interested in contributing to the project. The selected thematics consisted of the five main concepts (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Tagging system on website and description of the focus groups ^[37]

Main lessons learnt and future steps

During the three first years of the project, CENTRINNO has created a network of researchers and practitioners engaged in exploring new processes of activating and sustaining city level transformation, by running nine territorial playgrounds and developing a support infrastructure nurtured by peer-learning exchanges. The CENTRINNO framework was the spine of the research, as an object of dialogue to support the emergence of new knowledge and practices shared among and beyond the consortium of involved partners. The retrospective of its use journey illustrated the role of such design artefacts in shared knowledge generation and open discussions on future scenarios of systemic design projects in the context of locally-productive cities.

A meta-design artefact for cooperation, emergence and critical thinking

The design and uses of the framework have generated discussions and new forms of partnerships between members of the project. The creation of a common vocabulary is the result of exchanges and has permitted the creation of the DNA of the project, propagated in a hologrammatic manner during the duration of the project. The three types of action are strongly related with stakeholder engagement and community

development that enhanced the importance of people's role in systemic transformations.

The five selected concepts were interconnected umbrellas that evolve in parallel and that can host many conceptual backgrounds, worldviews, and that gain coherence when studied in a transdisciplinary manner. The diversity of the five concepts brought new interests and new profiles in the network that create new learnings and foster the emergence of ideas at the intersection of disciplines.

Meanwhile, the framework also generated forms of doubts and contestations inside the consortium that allowed for the emergence of constructive conversations. Some partners mentioned the framework might be too wide and conceptual to be understood and accessible for local stakeholders. Other debates occurred on the terminology and the differentiation between concepts and resources. As an example, some ambiguities could be felt with the "innovation space" concept, also used as "Fab City Hubs" or "Innovation" in some reports and co-creation activities. During the project, the knowledge on the concepts was consolidated by hosting regular discussions and external training sessions permitting a better appropriation from partners that then could re-interpret them and adapt its uses to fit with their local realities.

Enabling local transformations

The operationalisation of the framework endeavoured the realisation of local experimentations with effective impacts in respective territories. This was not only due to the structure of the framework itself but also in the way people engaged in the experimentation, their values, motivations and positions in the networks, as well as how they were supported all along the experimentation.

Local pilot stakeholders were onboarded as action-researchers as well as the designers and reporters of local actions, participating in a series of training and peer-learning activities, equipped with tools and platforms. They acted as interfaces between the local realities and the concepts. The dialogues with concept owners led to regular reciprocal learnings.

One good practice is the success of translating the concepts into sub-challenges tackled by the organisation of a series of micro-missions. Each pilot has engaged local stakeholders in new practices of mapping, making, learning, caring, connecting, reaching

a total of more than 150 challenges across the two first iterations. This has generated a better knowledge of resources, more awareness, new skills and synergies in the local communities.

The focus on the regeneration of old industrial sites into new creative and productive hubs has led to a better understanding of existing models and provoked the emergence of a new typology of place that acts as an interface and enabler of locally productive cities^[38]. Such places have roles for transmission, observation, empowerment, incubation and boost synergy-making with a strong diversity of stakeholders. Within CENTRINNO, each local pilot could weave relationships with public institutions, building a better awareness of local policy contexts, taking an active part in policy design processes, and anchoring the Fab City approach inside current policy ecosystems and action plans. As an instance, zooming into the Circular Economy concept in the sector of textile and clothing, both Milan and Blonduos pilots have reinforced their partnerships with private-public cooperations, by supporting community development for small-scale actors (makers, artisans, designers), respectively in the district area of Tortona and in the Icelandic Wool region.

Consolidating knowledge on future models of productive cities

CENTRINNO's experimentation is a playground for emerging new models of productive cities. The framework helped in structuring local interventions, collecting empiric data and permitting comparison of urban contexts, emphasising the importance of cultural diversity in city-transformation processes.

The overall approach is value-based and equips cities with visionary principles, methods, tools, and organisational tips that foster the engagement and dialogues between stakeholders in cross-cutting concepts, supporting the identification of gaps and opportunities for building their roadmap toward locally productive cities.

While the framework guaranteed to expand the perimeter of conceptual exploration spaces and collaboration zones, its application in context consolidated the definition of current trade-offs relating to convivial forms of production in cities that will need to be considered in further works. In particular, the socio-environmental impacts of local value-chains, especially fabrication processes, from ancestral techniques to new

technologies need to be better understood and shared among stakeholders. Collective instances such as the Fab City Hubs can create inventories of practices, share stories of making, and host activities of transmission and critical discussions on socio-environmental burdens. Beyond a better appropriation of techniques, cities in transition for more autonomy cannot escape to find adapted processes to define collectively what can or cannot be produced inside cities and in the perimeter of their bioregions ^[39].

References

1. Navracsics, T., Sucha, V., Wahlstroem, M., Stigson, B., Wijkman, A., Lechner, S., Masera, M., Hubbard, N., Bidoglio, G., Fink-Hooijer, F., Abousahl, S., Regling, K., Campolongo, F., Ratto, M., Nicholl, C., Fischer, G., Al, K. D., Porter, M., Luyckx, O., ... Jacometti, J. (2015, October 15). *The Challenge of Resilience in a Globalised World*. JRC Publications Repository. <https://doi.org/10.2788/010872>
2. Abbinnett, R. (2023). Gorz and Stiegler: Politics, ecology and the Neganthropocene. *Journal of Classical Sociology*, 23(2), 195–210.
3. Illich, I., & Lang, A. (1973). *Tools for conviviality*.
4. Kerschner, C., Wächter, P., Nierling, L., & Ehlers, M.-H. (2018). Degrowth and Technology: Towards feasible, viable, appropriate and convivial imaginaries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 1619–1636.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.07.147>
5. Stiegler, B. (2020). *Bifurquer: L'absolue nécessité*. Éditions Les Liens qui libèrent.
6. Sengers, F., Wieczorek, A. J., & Raven, R. (2019). Experimenting for sustainability transitions: A systematic literature review. *Technological Forecasting and Social*

- Change*, 145, 153–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.031>
7. Gallotti, R., Sacco, P., & De Domenico, M. (2021). Complex Urban Systems: Challenges and Integrated Solutions for the Sustainability and Resilience of Cities. *Complexity*, 2021, e1782354. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/1782354>
8. Muñoz Unceta, P., Diez Ladera, T., Wipoo, M., & Pazaitis, A. (2020). Centrinno WHITEPAPER. *Deliverable 1.1*.
https://centrinno.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Centrinno_WHITEPAPER_2.0_EUproject.pdf
9. Battistoni, C., Giraldo Nohra, C., & Barbero, S. (2019). A Systemic Design Method to Approach Future Complex Scenarios and Research Towards Sustainability: A Holistic Diagnosis Tool. *Sustainability*, 11(16), Article 16.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164458>
10. Furlan, C., Wandl, A., Cavalieri, C., & Unceta, P. M. (2022). Territorialising Circularity. In L. Amenta, M. Russo, & A. van Timmeren (Eds.), *Regenerative Territories: Dimensions of Circularity for Healthy Metabolisms* (pp. 31–49). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78536-9_2
11. Nohra, C. G., & Barbero, S. (2019). Systemic Design for territorial thinking. Circular urban transitions for post-industrial cities. *The Design Journal*, 22(sup1), 915–929.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14606925.2019.1595408>
12. Parisi, C., Beye, A., & Bekier, J. (2021). *The REFLOW Framework*.
<https://zenodo.org/record/5211533>

13. Brunner, P. H., & Rechberger, H. (2016). *Handbook of material flow analysis: For environmental, resource, and waste engineers*. CRC press.
14. Metabolic. (2023). *Centrinno Cartography*. My Site.
<https://www.centrinno-cartography.org>
15. Deserti, A., Real, M., & Schmittinger, F. (2022). *Co-creation for Responsible Research and Innovation: Experimenting with Design Methods and Tools*. Springer Nature.
16. Dorsch, M. J., & Flachsland, C. (2017). A Polycentric Approach to Global Climate Governance. *Global Environmental Politics*, 17(2), 45–64.
https://doi.org/10.1162/GLEP_a_00400
17. Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T., & Balogh, S. (2012). An Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mur011>
18. Foster, S., & Swiney, C. (2020). *City Networks and the Glocalization of Urban Governance*.
19. Amato, D., Kalathas, G., Vlachopoulou, C., Cingolani, F., Kühr, W., Armstrong, K., Diez, T., & Fontana Valenti, C. (2021). *Creative and productive hubs journal*. CENTRINNO Project; Deliverable D3.1.
20. Volumes. (2023). *Fab City Hub Toolkit*.
<https://volumesmedia.gitbook.io/fab-city-hub-toolkit/>
21. Schmidt-Lauber, B. (2012). Seeing, hearing, feeling, writing: Approaches and methods from the perspective of ethnological analysis of the present. A

- Companion to Folklore*, 559–578.
22. Dibbits, H. (2020). *Emotion networking: Heritage and citizenship education in the 21st century*1.
 23. AHK. (2023). *The Living Archive—Centrinno*. <https://livingarchive.centrinno.eu/>
 24. Make It Open. (2022). *Open Schooling*. <https://openschoolingnavigator.eu/>
 25. Sedin, C., Zurlo, F., & D'Ambrosio, S. (2022). A Systemic Approach to Proximity Through Design for Relations. *Relating Systems Thinking and Design Symposium*. <https://rdsymposium.org/a-systemic-approach-to-proximity-through-design-for-relations/>
 26. Cordis. (2019). *New CENTRALities in INDUSTRIAL areas as engines for inNOvation and urban transformation | CENTRINNO Project | Fact Sheet | H2020*. CORDIS | European Commission. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/869595>
 27. City, F. (2016). *Fab City whitepaper: Locally productive, globally connected self-sufficient cities*.
 28. Diez Ladera, T., Ferro, C., Niaros, V., Parikh, M., & Jusic, I. (2022, October 19). The Fab City Full Stack: A Multiscalar Framework for Distributed Production Strategies in Cities and Regions. In *Proceedings of the Fab 17 Research Papers Stream*. Hogeschool Rotterdam. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432027>
 29. Muñoz Unceta, P., Ingemann Henriksen, A., Nielsen, S., & Schulze, C. (2021). *CENTRINNO Framework*. CENTRINNO Project; Deliverable D1.2.
 30. *Centrinno—Industrial Citizen Revolution*. (n.d.). CENTRINNO. Retrieved 19 June 2023,

from <https://centrinno.eu/>

31. IAAC. (2021). *Centrinno Framework*. <https://framework.centrinno.eu/>
32. Costa, T., Guy, J., Ritter, F., Even-Zohar, J., Dibbits, H., & Olivotto, C. (2023). *Collective Results Sprint 2*. D4.3.
33. Wipoo, M., Hoekstra, N., Muñoz, P., Guy, J., Ritter, F., Even-Zohar, J., Dibbits, H., Becker, C., & Olivotto, C. (2021). *Collective Results Sprint 1*. D4.2.
34. Pazaitis, A., Niaros, V., & Singh, A. (2022). *Evaluation methodology*. CENTRINNO Project; Deliverable D5.1.
35. Pazaitis, A., Niaros, V., Petridis, P., & Singh, A. (2023). *Impact Assessment Report. Interim Report*. CENTRINNO Project; Deliverable D5.2.
36. Connell, J. P., & Kubisch, A. C. (1998). Applying a theory of change approach to the evaluation of comprehensive community initiatives: Progress, prospects, and problems. *New Approaches to Evaluating Community Initiatives*, 2(15–44), 1–16.
37. Centrinno Website. (2020). *Centrinno—Industrial Citizen Revolution*.
<https://centrinno.eu/>
38. Ferro, C., Muñoz Unceta, P., Fontana Valenti, C., Jusic, I., Cingolani, F., Diez Ladera, T., & Parikh, M. (2022, October 19). Fab City Hubs: Interfaces for community building and playgrounds for new innovative urban actions. In *Proceedings of the Fab 17 Research Papers Stream*. Hogeschool Rotterdam.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432052>
39. Thackara, J. (2019). Bioregioning: Pathways to Urban-Rural Reconnection. *She Ji: The*

Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation, 5(1), 15–28.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2019.01.002>

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